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MANAGEMENT OF BANK RISKS IN FINANCIAL MARKETS AND ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Since the crises experienced in the financial markets in recent years have brought the view to the fore that the financial sectors of developed and developing countries should be structured in a healthy way. The main elements of the new approach are creating a stable operating environment, developing financial markets, ensuring transparency, strengthening the national and international financial sector, and making joint efforts to prevent international financial crises. Within the scope of strengthening the national financial system, restructuring of banks, which traditionally constitute the most important institutions of the financial system in developing countries, has gained importance.

Risk management is of great importance for banks, which are the heart of financial markets. In order to increase their profitability, banks need to produce effective risk management systems that can meet the ever-increasing and changing demands of the market by constantly associating the capital-return-risk trio with each other. The purpose of risk management is to measure in advance the magnitude of losses that the markets may face in extraordinary situations while they are enduring their activities in order to be prepared for the extraordinary situations.

In this article, the purpose and importance of risk management in bank risks are defined and the measurement and management techniques of these risks are assessed. As such, after defining the concept of risks, the risks arising from the banking sector and the management methods of these risks are emphasized.

Keywords: Banking Sector, Bank risks, Risk Management

Review of the Risks Encountered in the Banking Sector

While the risks that banks are exposed to has a direct effect on their profitability, at the same time, they have an indirect effect on their capital adequacy and market shares. Effective management of such risks would allow to increase the profitability. If the bank complements a part of its profit to its capital, it will be able to increase its market share by strengthening its financial structure. The purpose of risk management is not to prevent the bank from taking risks. On the contrary, it is to increase profitability and financial performance by reducing the risks that the bank may face and preventing losses and increasing the extent of activities.

Bessis and Schroeck interpret the risks in banking as negative effects on those obtained from different impressions [3; 13]. According to Cade, risks in banking refer to the difference between the return of the banking system and the expected present value of the cash flows of these transactions [8]. From the perspective of bank, the risk is the condition where the expected income is lower than the expected return.

Financial risks are articulated as the probability of loss resulting from not achieving a financial target. Risk reflects uncertainty about exchange rates, interest rates, commodity prices, stock prices, credit quality, liquidity and an organization's access to finance. Financial risks are not independent of each other. For example, exchange rates and interest rates are often strongly linked. As such, this link should be taken into account when designing risk management models by managers. This link should be taken into account when designing risk management models by managers [26, pp. 1-30].

In general, banking activities pose many unique risks. These risks are risks such as a bank's loans, liquidity, trade, revenues and costs, earnings and solvency. The types of risks encountered by banks can be conveyed as interest rate risk, country risk, market risk, currency risk, liquidity risk, credit risk, management risk, operational risk, legal risk, reputation risk and bankruptcy risk.

Interest Rate Risk: it is the price that determines the balance of supply and demand in the economy. For

normal goods, rising prices increase supply and decrease demand. On the other hand, falling prices reduce supply and increase demand. The price of money, that is, the property of banks, is assessed as the interest rate. The change in interest rates according to market conditions generates instability in terms of both the economic balance and profitability of banks due to the fact that interest rates provide the balance of savings and investment in an economy. The banks, on the other hand, provide the transfer of individuals who have surplus funds, that is, individuals who have savings, by collecting the surplus funds, as meeting the fund demand of individuals who want to invest or want to consume, and profit from the sale in between. The difference in the price, namely the interest rate, constructs complications and risks for banks. Interest rate risk is income or capital risk arising from market floating interest rates [16, pp.62-70]. The values of both the bank's income and its on-balance sheet and off-balance sheet (OBS) items change when the present value of future cash flows changes when interest rates change [2]. There seem to be two basic techniques that banks can apply to interest rate risk: 1) Equalizing the maturities of asset and liability items as much as possible; 2) Using different derivative instruments such as options and swaps by the bank. Although the first method seems to be the most effective way to eliminate interest rate risk, it is quite difficult to implement, because banks generally provide short-term resources and long-term loans due to the nature of their activities.

Country Risk: In national or international credit transactions, it is referred as the failure to fulfill some or all of its obligations on time due to the economic, social and political structure of the country in which the person or institution operates. Apart from possible changes in fiscal and monetary policies, factors such as political crises, wars, and government changes also have an impact on the behavior of investors. Generally, international investors are more affected by political risk. While measuring country risk, ratings given by international rating agencies to countries can be used, or a method called the scoring method can be utilized. Assuming the rapid growth of international lending and foreign direct investment, country risk analysis has become essential for international creditors and investors [11].

Market Risk: This risk arises in value changes in assets due to systematic factors and refers to the risk arising from changes in exchange rates, interest rates and asset prices when assets and liabilities change, that is, when they are used for commercial purposes [9]. For banks, market risk arises when they actively use their assets and liabilities in buying and trading to make short-term profits, aside from long-term investment and funding purposes. According to the Basel Agreement, market risk represents "the risk of loss on balance sheet and off-balance sheet items resulting from changes in market prices" [24, pp.12-15].

Currency Risk: Currency risk is the possibility of loss due to future exchange rate changes. In other words, they are the risks that may arise from unexpected behavior in exchange rates. When banks perform transactions such as accepting deposits or lending

in other currencies, they are faced with currency risk as well as interest rate and credit risks. Exchange rate risk adversely affects banks' liabilities due to changes in exchange rates. This risk exists in all foreign exchange transactions with parties residing abroad [10]. In order to be manage the currency risk, banks can use different derivative instruments such as futures, forwards, options and swap contracts, and securities from different countries can be included in the international portfolios of investors [23].

Liquidity Risk: This risk arises from the bank's inability to adjust the decrease in its liabilities well or not having sufficient resources to cope with the increase in its assets. Banks that are short of liquidity may not be able to raise the necessary funds in a short time by increasing their liabilities or converting their assets into cash at a reasonable price. Banks have to maintain sufficient funds or plan where and how the funds can be obtained in order to fulfill their obligations under normal and non-normal conditions. The liquidity requirements of the bank differ depending on various factors such as fields of activity, funding sources and balance sheet structure. However, regardless of their field of activity and structure, all banks should comprehensively determine, measure, monitor and control their liquidity requirements. During the last financial crisis, many banks experienced difficulties because they were not able to properly manage their liquidity despite having sufficient capital. Post-crisis, higher liquidity cost, larger funding margins, higher volatility and decreased market confidence have prompted financial institutions to allocate more resources to improve their liquidity risk management capabilities [18, pp. 186-204].

Credit Risk: Credit risk refers to the situation faced by the bank due to the partial or complete failure of bank customers to fulfill their contractual obligations. Overall, it is assumed that the credit risk of long-term loans and bonds is higher than that of short-term loans and bonds [7]. In the process of measuring, monitoring and managing credit risk: 1) Continuous management of various portfolios bearing credit risk should be carried out, the determination of the provisions is required to be allocated, the determination of all loan portfolios should have a system to monitor its composition and quality. 2) Consistent internal risk ratings for characteristics, scales and activities should be utilized via scoring systems/models. If the entire principal and interest of the loan given by the bank or the bond received is collected in a timely and complete manner, the bank will not face credit risk.

Management Risk: This type of risk that arises depending on the good or bad management of the bank. The success of a bank is directly related to the knowledge, skills and experience of the managers. If managers make the wrong decision, it will likely cause the actual cash flow to deviate negatively from the expected cash flow. As the expected profitability of well-managed banks will be higher, investors will demand more for their stocks.

Operational Risk: It is defined as the possibility of loss or damage that may result from errors and irregularities due to disruptions in internal controls, failure to act in accordance with time and conditions by the

bank management and personnel [12]. errors in bank management, errors and disruptions in information technology systems, and disasters such as earthquakes, fires, floods. External risks, fraud incidents related to third parties other than the bank, changes and gaps in legal regulations related to possible risk issues, damages caused by social turmoil, money laundering, abuse of websites by external interventions are examples for the operational risk.

Reputational Risk: This risk arises from bank failures or non-compliance with existing laws and regulations. This type of risk can cause significant harm to banks, as it is critical for banks to gain and maintain the trust of their customers and market participants [5].

Bankruptcy Risk: Such risks arise when banks do not have sufficient capital to cope with a sudden decrease in the value of their assets relative to their liabilities. The fact that banks have more capital than they borrow and therefore operate with low leverage makes it easier for them to withstand negative interest rate movements and losses from bad credit.

Management of bank risks and its Methods

The issue of risk management has come to a point where many studies and regulations have been made, since it has a decisive role in the international crises that have occurred in recent years. The main reasons for this development are volatility in the markets, developments in information technology, increase in transaction volume and developments in derivative instruments. The risk management process consists of the stages of defining and measuring risks, establishing and implementing risk policies and implementation procedures, analyzing and monitoring risks, reporting, researching, confirming and auditing within the framework of the principles determined jointly by the bank's senior management and risk management group and approved by the board of directors. The purpose of risk management can be expressed as being able to pre-measure the size of the loss that the bank may face in extraordinary situations experienced by the markets, to establish systems that will ensure that the loss is avoided as little as possible, and to take measures to avoid loss.

Methods in Risk Management: The methods used in risk management are traditional risk management, + portfolio theory, and Value at Risk (VaR) methods. The most important of these methods is the Value at Risk (VaR) method.

1. Traditional Risk Management - Traditional risk management deals with the main types of risk that banks manage. These are fundamental risks such as currency risk, interest rate risk, liquidity risk. Interest rate risk is the change in revaluation prices of asset and liability items as a result of interest rate changes [20]. The maturity structures, interest structures and return/cost conditions of the items are different. Frequently used traditional risk management methods are gap analysis, duration analysis, statistical analysis and scenario analysis.

1.1. GAP Analysis - it is the difference/ratio of interest-sensitive assets and liabilities. The fact that balance sheet items are sensitive to interest means that it will change in the same direction and in an amount

close to that change with the change in the interest carried by that item [27]. Interest-sensitive items are used in GAP ratios [25]. An item is interest-sensitive indicates that it has little time to maturity or that it is a variable-interest item with a very short period.

✓ $GAP = (\text{Interest Sensitive Assets}) - (\text{Interest Sensitive Liabilities})$

✓ $GAP = (\text{Interest-Sensitive Assets}) / (\text{Interest-Sensitive Liabilities})$

With the two separate formulas above, the GAP can be analyzed as a difference, as well as GAP ratio can also be obtained. If the GAP ratio is higher than one, the GAP is positive and interest-sensitive assets are more than interest-sensitive liabilities. In this case, an increase in interest rates will create a profit for the bank, and a decrease will create a loss. It is necessary to calculate the GAP ratios for various maturities.

1.2. Duration Analysis- It is one of the techniques used to measure interest rate risk among traditional risk management techniques. The duration analysis, which was first used in the analysis of bond markets, has recently been used in the analysis of bank balance sheets [4]. Duration is time-weighted period. In other words, the duration of a balance sheet item is the weighted average of all the cash flows that that item will generate during its maturity, discounted to its present value, over the periods during which those cash flows will occur [6]. Duration analysis is a more useful analysis than GAP analysis because it takes into account not only the change in net income but also the change in the prices of assets or liabilities. However, there are points where the duration analysis is also limited, hence, it neglects risks other than interest risk [1].

1.3. Statistical Analysis- Statistical analysis has a limitation in accessing data. Since the price data of the securities that are normally traded in the market are available, the analysis is also limited to the market price risk [17]. However, the volatility experienced in the past data can sometimes lead us to erroneous results. Using only historical data keeps us informed of past market conditions, however, using historical data to predict the future can lead to erroneous results [22, pp.95–112].

1.4. Scenario Analysis - By producing various scenarios, this type of analysis measure how the basic performance indicators of the bank have changed over the certain time period. These scenarios can be produced as many different variations. As a result of the worst-case scenarios, the maximum loss that the bank can suffer is attempted to be determined. Scenario analysis relies heavily on individual abilities and experience factor in generating and evaluating probabilities [21].

1.5. Portfolio Theory - It allows multiple risks to be handled together and with their effects on each other; however, the data issue may come up again. Although it is easy to calculate the risk-free return or expected market value, calculating the risk factor (the ratio of the covariance between the portfolio return and the security's return to the variance of the portfolio return) to be used in the calculation of the risk premium of a security can be problematic. In order to calculate this risk factor, the returns on new assets should be known, the returns on all existing assets should be known, and a data set

covering a sufficiently long period should be found for the risk techniques to be used to be reliable [15, pp.1743-1759]. Considering that beta values need to be recalculated every time the portfolio changes, it is perceived that the portfolio analysis method requires a large amount of transactions and a significant amount of data on a regular basis.

1.6. Value at Risk (VaR) - Since VaR systems become more widespread, they are tried to be developed in a way that includes credit, liquidity, cash flow (for private companies) risks, apart from measuring market risk, which is the first purpose of development. Credit Metrics, developed by JP Morgan for measuring credit risk, can be given as an example of studies in this direction [14]. This method expresses the highest loss that may occur within a certain period in a certain confidence interval in financial markets, with a forward-looking view, in a type that can be understood by everyone - as money value [19, pp. 507-528]. In JP Morgan's Risk Metrics document, the concept of VaR is explained as follows: "It is an estimate of how much the portfolio could lose value over a given period of time, within a predetermined confidence interval. The potential timeframe could be 1 day for typical market transactions or a month or longer for portfolio management purposes." VaR gives the chance to combine the risk arising from different positions and risk factors and to express it in a single value. In addition, VaR takes into account the correlation between risk factors, and if there are risks that eliminate/reduce each other, the total risk is found to be less.

Conclusion

Banks have to manage their risks very well in today's economy because a crisis that arises as a result of poorly managed risks in one of the financial sectors can spread to other sectors in a very short time and harm the economy of the country. By means of protective and preventive policies, banks can minimize the losses that the risk may cause before or after the risk occurs. However, banks can never operate with zero risk because this is contrary to the understanding of banking. The main purpose of banks is to maximize their returns in return for a certain risk borne. Banks are required to have an effective risk management in order to maintain the financial stability of both national and international markets. Many banks that do not have effective risk management may face huge losses. The increase in international competition, technological progress, and the diversification of classical banking with new products and services have led to a differentiation of the risks faced by banks, which are among the biggest actors of financial markets. Therefore, the risks must be carefully identified, measured and monitored.

In addition, the management of these risks and the supervision and control of the sector should be carried out efficiently and effectively. For this reason, risk management systems, methodologies and technologies have started to be developed under the leadership of BIS and internationally active financial institutions. In financial markets, banks hold a higher share in the developed countries. For this reason, the safe operation of

banks becomes much more important for the whole economy.

After the last crisis period, necessary studies have been started in order to provide a strong infrastructure in terms of risk management, which is of vital importance for banks. As a result of the studies put into practice in order to bring the banking system to a healthier structure, the expected results have begun to be obtained. Although the structural problems of the banking system continue, the system's resilience against crises and external shocks has increased more than in the last crisis periods.

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THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN HUMAN CAPITAL FORMATION

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Abstract

The article emphasizes the growing importance of education in the formation of human capital. The authors analyze the fundamental studies in the research field of human capital and emphasize general aspects and categories specific to them. The paper briefly covers the relationship between education and the different dimensions of economic growth and social well-being.

Keywords: human capital, knowledge-based economy, human capabilities, education, income.

In the 21st century, the human factor — or, to be more precise, human capital — is involving more and more concern as a decisive factor of economic growth. That is partly because human capital is mainly characterized by knowledge, and the world economy is rapidly transforming into a knowledge-based economy. According to P. Drucker, “the knowledge society will inevitably be more competitive than any society we know”.² Knowledge, as the main source of wealth, defines a new socio-economic order on a global scale. In addition, the new age is often referred to as the “digital age”, and advances in digital technology are the product of human knowledge and intellect.

To understand the concept of human capital more clearly, it is important to distinguish it from physical capital. Physical capital refers to measurable man-made goods that are intended for use in the production process, while human capital means a human’s entire capacity that makes his efforts beneficial for an economy and society as a whole and is normally unmeasurable. Money, buildings, machines, equipment, and inventory

that are involved in running a business are some examples of physical capital. In addition, human capital, as an intangible asset of a business, consists of knowledge, skills, experience (whether innate or acquired), and the well-being of its employees.

Besides, physical capital is viewed from a cost perspective, while human capital is viewed from a profit perspective. Moreover, unlike physical capital, human capital is directly related to the individual. That is, only a person can own human capital. Another important point is that this form of capital is not lost as the result of being used in the production process; on the contrary, the more cycles it goes through, the more it is renewed and enriched. And it can depreciate only in cases of long-term unemployment or an inability to keep up with or adopt new technologies.

Scientific research on human capital appeared after the work of Reuben Gronau and Gary Becker in the 1950s and 1960s of the last century, but the history of human capital has long been dated. The very first thoughts related to the concept of human capital were

² Turriago-Hoyos A., Thoene U., and Surendra A. (2016). “Knowledge Workers and Virtues in Peter Drucker’s Management Theory”, SAGE Open, January-March, p. 1–9.